

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B348
Date: 23/4 February 2008
Take Off: 19:49:48Z 03:06:39Z
Landing: 01:28:53Z 04:35:32Z
Flight Time 5h39m05 1h28m53

Campaign: CLPX II

Operating Area: Brooks Range and North Slope Ground Sites, Alaska

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jon Taylor	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chem	Bob Wells	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
8	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
9	CVI / Nephelometers	Rob King	Met Office
10	DEIMOS	Dave Pollard	Met Office
11	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 2	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
13	Dropsondes	Doug Anderson	FAAM

Flight Track:

B348 Track 23-FEB-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B348
 Date: 23/02/08
 Project: CPLXII
 Location: North of Barrow

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
191311		GPS lock on	0.29 kft	217	5 mins outside
191640		asp open	0.29 kft	217	
191735		engine start	0.28 kft	217	
192756		engine shutdown	0.28 kft	217	
193511		engine start 2	0.28 kft	217	
194104		power change	0.28 kft	217	
194256		taxi	0.28 kft	217	start
194948		T/O	0.27 kft	218	from Fairbanks
200452		contrailing	23.3 kft	336	
202038		BBR	24.0 kft	332	Exposed
210403		BBR	24.7 kft	325	covered
211041	221625	Run 1	28.0 kft	323	
211253		Sonde1	28.0 kft	332	
212036		BBR	28.0 kft	344	Exposed
212545		Sonde 2	28.0 kft	342	
214043		Sonde 3	28.0 kft	342	
215543		Sonde 4	28.0 kft	341	
220947		Sonde 5	28.0 kft	344	
221650	222520	Run 1.1	28.0 kft	359	
222455		Sonde 6	28.0 kft	001	
222548	225853	Profile 1	28.0 - -.29 kft	000	
222640		BBR	27.0 kft	004	covered
223833		Profile 1	16.2 kft	000	interrupt
224022		Profile 1	16.2 kft	188	resume
225156		Copilot GPS	4.7 kft	187	temporarily down
225900	232300	Run 2	-.21 - -.30 kft	181	
231622		qnh 1027	-.27 kft	188	
231730		BBR	-.25 kft	189	Exposed
232331	251451	Run 2.1	-.28 - -.53 kft	166	turn towards barrow
233422		qnh 1029	-.35 kft	171	
233802		qnh 1030	-.34 kft	171	
245940		qnh	-.54 kft	168	1038
251906	252009	Run 3	-.10 - -.14 kft	057	at Barrow
252417	252540	Run 4	-.32 - -.06 kft	236	
252853		Land	-.64 kft	270	at Barrow
030639		T/O	-.66 kft	359	from Barrow
030639	033535	Profile 2	4.3 - 26.9 kft	359	
043532		Land	0.24 kft	359	at Fairbanks

B348 Track 23-FEB-08

PAFA -> PABR - Overview

NavData Cycle 2008-2 Expires: Thursday, 13 March 2008.

Scale: 1:6008471 (1 inch = 82.41 naut mi). Printed on 22 Feb 2008

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.3.0.0

SORTIE BRIEF

CLPX-II – Land and Sea Ice Surface Property Studies.

Flight B348
Date: 23rd Feb 2008

Mission Scientist: J Taylor

Science Aims: To characterise the land/sea ice surface properties under an overpass of the IASI satellite at 2119Z. Also to overfly a sea ice monitoring site just north of Barrow.

Weather: Cloud free conditions at all levels.

Waypoints:

Alpha 70 °48.7'N 156° 12.2'W
Bravo 77°N 162°W
Charlie 71°22.25'N 156°32.20'W

Sortie Details:

1. 1945Z (1045L) Take off and transit to arrive at ALPHA at FL280 (90mins)
2. 2115Z (1215L) Straight and level run from ALPHA to BRAVO at FL280 dropping 5 sondes at times (0,15,30,45,55) (60mins)
3. 2215Z (1315L) Profile descent to end at BRAVO at 50ft 1000ft/min descent (35mins)
4. 2250Z (1350L) Straight and level run from BRAVO to ALPHA at 100ft (90mins)
5. 0020Z (1520L) Fly series of passes over ice station at point CHARLIE (30mins)
6. 0050Z (1550L) Land at Barrow for refuel
7. 0250Z (1750L) Transit back to Fairbanks. (90mins)
8. 0420Z (1920L) Land at Fairbanks

CLPX II

B348 23rd Feb 2008 Debrief

Mission Scientist: Jonathan P Taylor

The aim of the flight was to study the sea ice NW of Barrow. The transit to the area was at FL240 and there was extensive cloud below the aircraft during the entire transit with variable cirrus above.

Way point Alpha was defined over the land South of Barrow and we climbed to FL280 to start this run. As we approached the start of the run the cloud dissipated at all levels and we kept cloud free conditions for the remainder of the sortie with the exception of ice crystals in low concentrations trapped in the surface layer.

A long run was flown from Alpha to a point at 79N 162W during which time 6 drop sondes were launched to characterise the atmospheric state. There was pretty good visibility to the surface but there was a distinct layer above the surface where vis was poorer.

The profile to 50ft over the sea ice clearly indicated the presence of small concentrations of small hexagonal columns which resulted in optical phenomena being seen. These poorer visibility conditions were in the form of isolated pockets which we flew through and noted the positions. The run back South was flown at 100ft above the sea ice and lasted 2hrs 15mins. There were isolated leads but a fairly consistent ice structure all the way back to Barrow.

After arriving back at Barrow we flew a short run over land and then flew two runs at 500ft over the ice station site operated by Univ. of Alaska, Fairbanks.

After the refuel stop at Barrow a scientific profile ascent was flown up to FL260 and then a straight transit back to Fairbanks.

Summary

The weather conditions were excellent with good cloud free conditions. The only exception being low concentrations of ice crystals in the boundary layer. All dropsondes worked and the high level runs were coordinated with IASI and NOAA overpasses. The only instrument snag was Deimos where the 24 and 50GHz channels were intermittent throughout the sortie and only post flight analysis will show whether we were able to get any useful data from Deimos for the flight.

Mission Scientist's Log

CCPX-II

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B348** Date 23/2/08 Name Jon Taylor Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1049 local	1949 Z.				T/O @ FAIRBANKS. 6/8 Ci above 4/8 St below just above top.
2009	F2240				Contracting in Transit
20130	F2240.	330		66° 6' N 149° 36' W	8/8 St over mountains. clear skies above
		T = -50.18 Td = -48.49			
					Reverses 246 Hz channel is u/s. 506 Hz on but usual noise levels.
202832	F2240.	330		67° 30' N 157° 12' W	still contracting some Ci on horizon 8/8 St below some wisps breaking tho top. T = -69.66°C Td = -52.88 mds 12/248°
203120					Over Ci clouds 7/8 Ci below still contracting.
204130					Ci clld below is thinning still some higher stuff on horizon. still 8/8 St over mountains.
204936	F2240				still contracting 8/8 St below thin Ci on horizon climbing to F2280

033535

Mission Scientist's Log

CLPX-II

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.348** Date 23/2/08 Name Jon Tye Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
206926					506Hz a/cnty dropped
2210000	sh. AMIES				246Hz channel showing something new AMIES backup
210846					old clearing below now
211041	R1	FL280	323	70° 68' N 158° 6' W.	St Run 1 from Alpha to Bravo v. patchy cloud below can see some clearly. horizon shows clear demarcation suggesting a change in moisture.
211252		FL280	332		Sonde 1 gone
211617		FL280			Over land at Barrow
			346		change of heading. clear below & above still containing.
212563	R1	FL280	361	210846 157° 06' W 72° 06' N 157° 12' W.	Sonde 2 gone. Sonde 1 splashdown still clear below & above.
212654					large lead below.
212913					large lead below 72° 30 157° 02' W.
213006					50 GHz channel dropped out 24 GHz looking ok
213635		FL280			Sonde 2 on ground! still clear above & below.

Mission Scientist's Log

CAPT-II

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.368** Date 23/2/08 Name Jen Taylor Page 3 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
213730		F280	342		still clear above & below.
214045	R1	F280	342	73° 30' N 158° 36' W	Sonde 3 gone still clear above and below.
					Large clear noted large debris in CO as passed lead/seawire bands at 2115.
215505	R4	F280	341	76° 56' N 160° W	Sonde 4 gone still clear above & below.
220558					S4 on ground
220569	R4	F280	344	76° 18' N 161° 18' W	Sonde 5 gone. T = -52 td = -65.
221305					large leads below.
221605	R4	F280			Interrupt Run 1 for Hdg change
221650	R1.2	F280	359	77° N 162° W	Restart Run 1.2 on new heading still clear above & below.
222457	R4.2	F280	001	79° 18' N 161° 56' W	Sonde 6 gone T = 51 td = -86.18°
222520	R1.2	F280			stop at End of R1.2
222548	P1	F280	003	78° N 162° W	stop P1 ↓ to 1000ft
2230					Interrupt P1 ↓ 1000ft on 1008hPa
224022		1000ft			Restart P1 ↓ on 1000 1008hPa

Mission Scientist's Log

CPX-11

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B328** Date **23/2/08** Name **Jon Tread** Page **4** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
224358		12360	187		P1 ↓ on 1008 ft heading back along line of prev. outbound back towards borrow.
224738	P1 ↓	8650			into slightly moister haze on 1008 ft still totally cloud free conditions
225853		50 ft			Some ice at coast on ZDC Early P1
225900	R2	100 ft	181		1st run R2 P100 ft. 500 ft channel cave back at bottom of profile.
230843	R2	100 ft			over sea ice $T = -29^{\circ}C$ $Td = -28.8^{\circ}$
232117					still seeing melt runs at 22:50 either side of ZDC seeing small ice flow channels Intercept R2 chase holes
232300	R2	100 ft			Intercept R2 chase holes
232331		166			Intercept R2 Intercept R2
232237		100 ft	189	7600 16055E W	ice comes from 10-20 to 50 ft on ZDC
					ice temp colder near coast than out to north.
23268					vis improved ZDC gone ↓ no optical penetration

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.368** Date 23/2/08 Name Jon Aron Page 5 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					2R comes ↑.
235284		100ft	171		Visibility deteriorated again. v. short passage to y lower vis
235706					Excellent VIS.
240010	R2	100ft	170	75° N 160° W	Vis decreasing again optical phenomena back again
241053					Sub passed over large ice area lead.
244559					over v. rough lumpy ice.
244631					Slightly smoother sea ice.
2446720					Smoother ice square again now $T = -30.5K$ $t_{air} = -30.12^{\circ}C$.
	R2	100ft.			End Run 2
					Now do some runs over pt Charlie to verify ice status.
251906	R3	500ft	057		Station 3 over Charlie
252009					End R3
252417	R4	500ft	236		Station 4
222540	R4	500ft.	-		End Run 4
2528					Land

270649

Take off / shut down chub out to Fairbanks

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B348

Date: 23/02/08	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 18:07:00	DAU1 Time: N/A	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: N/A	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
																2DC, 2DP, SID1 only	
19:50						noise											
19:52:36				2	2	400	4075	1200								3, 8 FL030	
19:53:19				10	1	800	4508	1200								3,8 FL050	
19:53:50				2	1	700	1308	1600								3,8 FL060	
19:55:16				1	0		0									FL090	
19:55:40				0	0		0									FL100	
19:56:10				1	3	600	0									3,8 FL110	
19:56:48				0	0		0									FL120	
19:58:33				8	23	450	216	800								8 FL150	
19:59:13				10	1.5	450	7808	800								8 FL160	
19:59:52				80	200	400	500	800								8,4 FL170	
20:00:20				0	0		0									FL180	
20:01:20				20	17	475	2725	400								11,8 FL190	
20:02:15				80	100	275	6541	275								11,8 FL200	
20:03:10				2	1	450	2666	450								11,4 FL210	
20:04:03				0	0.5	650	3991									4 FL220	
20:04:40				20	1	650	10775	650								4 FL230	
20:05:38				20	3	450	21300	450								4 FL240	
20:07																2DP TOO COLD/NOISY - OFF	
21:10:40				0	0											START R1 FL280	
21:12:53				1	0											SONDE 1	
21:25:48				0	0											SONDE 2	
21:34:00				0	0												
21:40:43				0	0											SONDE 3	
21:45:00				0	0												
21:50:00				0	0												
21:55:43				0	0											SONDE 4	
22:00:00				0	0												
22:05:00				0	0												
22:09:48				0	0											SONDE 5	
22:20:00				0	0												
22:24:55				0	0											SONDE 6	
22:25:48				0	0											FL280 START P2	
22:26:40				0	0											FL270	
22:27:36				0	0											FL260	
22:28:42				0	0											FL250	
22:30:05				0	0											FL240	
22:31:18				0	0											FL230	
22:32:21				8	0											FL220	
22:33:21				0	0											FL210	

PCASP Reference Volts = N/A	FFSSP Reference Volts = Not fitted	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 1.75	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = N/A	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = N/A
PCASP Flow rate = N/A		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = 1.0	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = N/A	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = N/A
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = Not fitted	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = 3V		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B348

Date: 23/02/08	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 18:07:00	DAU1 Time: N/A	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: N/A	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
22:34:20				0		0										FL200	
22:35:20				0		0										FL190	
22:36:20				0		0										FL180	
22:37:23				0		0										FL170	
22:38:32				1		0										FL160	
22:41:15				0		0										FL150	
22:42:18				0		0										FL140	
22:43:22				0		0										FL130	
22:44:24				1		0										FL120	
22:45:27				1		0										FL110	
22:46:25				1		0										FL100	
22:47:13				0		0										FL090	
22:48:09				0		0										FL080	
22:49:09				0		0										FL070	
22:50:15				1		0										FL060	
22:51:28				1		0										FL050	
22:52:40				1		0										FL040	
22:53:40				1		0										FL030	
22:54:40				2		0										FL020	
22:55:50				20		0										FL010	
22:56:20				30		24	250								6,11	FL005	
22:58:00				80		35	200								6,11		
22:59:00				80		42	175								6,11	START R2 100FT AGL	
23:01:00				80		18	200								11		
23:04:00				70		2	175								11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:08:00				60		3.5	175								6,11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:10:00				20		20	175								11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:12:00				20		0										Optical phenomenon reported	
23:15:00				30		0.5	175								11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:18:00				30		2.5	225								6	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:21:00				40		11	200								11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:24:00				30		3	200								11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:27:00				30		18	175								6,11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:30:00				90		67	225								6,11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:33:00				30		9	225								6,11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:40:00				40		8	125								6,11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:42:00				100		70	225								6,11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:44:00				30		15	225								6,11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:47:00				100		183	175								6,11	Optical phenomenon reported	
23:50:00				20		0										Vis much improved, no optical phenomenon	
23:53:00				200		91	225								6,11	Vis deteriorated again.	
23:56:00				90		26	125								11	Vis better	
23:58:00				20		0											

PCASP Reference Volts = N/A	FFSSP Reference Volts = Not fitted	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 1.75	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = N/A	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = N/A
PCASP Flow rate = N/A		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = 1.0	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = N/A	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = N/A
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = Not fitted	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = 3V		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B348 **T/O:** 19:49:48
Date of flight: 23/02/08 **Land:** 03:06:39

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		NOT FITTED
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = b348_tas</p> <p>Start = 194500 End = 253000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 252848 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 2657</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = b348_tas Y = (X+1) = B348_tas_2d</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B348
Date of Flight: 23/02/08

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	Note instrument problems This flight so data not Expected to be any use.
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	New software used Min size = Not asked Vol flow rate = Not asked Instrument problems this Flight. 194500 253000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = _tas_2d Y = X+1 = _tas_2d_pcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Y Use flight_plot to check.

B348_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

17:33:24.38 --- - - -
17:33:24.41 --- - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
17:33:24.41 --- - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn /
    Period / tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
17:33:24.41 --- - - - +++ Flight no. B348
17:33:24.41 --- - - -
17:33:42.03 SWS - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
17:33:44.56 USH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
17:33:46.65 LSH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
17:33:56.44 SWS - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to
    600ms.
17:33:57.98 SWS - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to
    600ms.
17:34:00.28 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
    Recording!
17:34:00.29 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
    Recording!
17:34:00.30 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
    Recording!
17:34:17.12 USH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to
    600ms.
17:34:21.39 USH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to
    600ms.
17:34:28.08 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to
    600ms.
17:34:32.28 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to
    600ms.
17:34:39.41 --- - - - Reset shutters.
17:34:44.81 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
17:34:45.65 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
17:34:45.67 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
17:34:51.29 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
    Recording!
17:34:52.11 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
    Recording!
17:34:52.33 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
    Recording!
17:45:08.41 --- - - - *** box temp +14c
17:45:11.78 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
17:45:11.78 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
17:45:12.45 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
17:45:12.64 USH - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
    measurement.
17:45:12.81 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
    measurement.
17:45:13.27 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
    measurement.
17:45:18.05 --- - - - Reset shutters.
17:45:18.43 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
    Recording!
17:45:18.57 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
    Recording!
17:45:19.12 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
    Recording!
17:45:23.62 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:45:24.06 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:45:24.35 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:45:30.12 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
    Recording!

```

17:45:30.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:45:30.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:46:32.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:46:33.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:46:33.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:46:39.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:46:39.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:46:40.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:11:25.19	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
18:11:29.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:11:30.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:11:30.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:11:35.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:11:36.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:11:36.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:11:52.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp +5c
18:29:07.96	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
18:29:13.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:29:13.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:29:14.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:29:20.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:29:20.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:29:20.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:29:37.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp +1c
18:29:59.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:29:59.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:29:59.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:32:02.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:32:02.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:32:02.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:32:05.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:32:05.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:32:05.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:40:05.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
18:40:11.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
18:40:47.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
18:40:55.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
18:41:29.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
18:41:34.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
18:41:44.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:41:45.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:41:45.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:41:52.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
18:41:54.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.

18:41:57.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
18:42:01.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** SHUTTING DOWN...
18:42:01.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor control quit.
18:42:29.24	---	-	-	-	-	
18:42:29.24	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
18:42:29.24	---	-	-	-	-	+++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn /
						Period / tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
18:42:29.24	---	-	-	-	-	+++ Flight no. B348
18:42:29.25	---	-	-	-	-	
18:42:37.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
18:42:49.83	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
18:42:53.10	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
18:42:54.92	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
18:43:21.74	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 116.453
18:43:36.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
18:43:36.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
18:43:36.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
18:43:42.85	SWS	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
18:43:44.53	SWS	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
18:43:47.51	USH	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
18:43:48.58	USH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
18:43:51.22	LSH	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
18:43:52.86	LSH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
18:44:03.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:44:03.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:44:03.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:44:12.90	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
18:44:18.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:44:18.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:44:18.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:44:24.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:44:25.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:44:25.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:44:42.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -1c
19:06:42.23	SWS	116.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
19:06:43.91	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:06:46.09	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
19:06:47.88	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:06:55.56	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 117.397
19:06:56.67	SWS	117.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:07:06.64	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
19:07:11.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:07:12.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:07:12.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:07:18.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:07:18.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

19:07:19.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:07:48.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -4c
19:07:59.40	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
19:07:59.41	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
19:08:03.16	USH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
19:08:03.19	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
19:08:07.31	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
19:08:07.32	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
19:08:11.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:08:11.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:08:11.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:08:14.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:08:15.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:08:16.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:08:25.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:08:25.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:08:25.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:08:27.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:08:30.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:08:30.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:08:47.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -4c
19:08:52.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:08:52.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:08:52.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:09:24.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:09:24.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:09:24.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:09:26.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:09:26.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:09:26.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:10:46.57	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:18:45.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** note faulty telescope position indicator
19:28:06.25	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
19:28:12.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:28:12.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:28:12.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:28:15.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:28:16.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:28:17.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:28:27.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -6c

19:28:37.56	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
19:28:37.57	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
19:28:47.43	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
19:28:47.44	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
19:28:56.64	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
19:28:56.65	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
19:29:02.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:02.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:02.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:03.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:29:04.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:29:04.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:44:13.38	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
19:44:18.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:44:18.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:44:18.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:44:18.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:44:20.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:44:21.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:44:21.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:44:27.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:44:31.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:44:47.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -7c
19:51:51.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** t/o 194948
19:54:35.31	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
19:54:40.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:54:40.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:54:40.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:54:41.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:54:43.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:54:43.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:54:45.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:54:45.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:54:45.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:57:15.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
19:57:37.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
19:59:50.00	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
20:00:45.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:00:45.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:00:45.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:00:47.31	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
20:00:51.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:00:51.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:00:51.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:00:53.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:00:54.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

20:00:54.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:00:56.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:00:56.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:00:56.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:05:12.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -8c
20:12:34.33	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
20:12:38.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:12:38.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:12:38.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:12:40.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:12:41.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:12:41.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:13:05.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -9c
20:15:02.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** solid deck of Sc below
20:23:37.17	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
20:23:41.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:23:41.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:23:41.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:23:43.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:23:44.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:23:44.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:23:56.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -9c
20:26:12.80	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
20:26:13.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
20:29:42.09	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
20:29:43.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
20:29:49.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:29:49.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:29:49.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:29:51.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:29:52.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:29:52.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:33:37.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -10c
20:33:50.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:33:50.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:33:50.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:33:52.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:33:53.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:33:53.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:39:29.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:39:29.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:39:29.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:39:30.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:39:31.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:39:32.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:39:36.42	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
20:39:37.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
20:39:50.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -10c
20:41:53.94	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
20:41:54.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
20:42:00.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:42:01.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:54:39.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -11c
20:54:43.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:54:43.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:54:43.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:54:45.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:54:45.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:54:46.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:03:07.29	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
21:03:08.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.

21:03:46.79	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
21:03:47.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:04:33.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -9c
21:04:43.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:04:43.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:04:43.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:04:45.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:04:46.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:04:46.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:08:33.82	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
21:08:34.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:10:39.92	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
21:10:48.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run 1
21:15:51.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:15:51.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:15:51.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:15:53.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:15:53.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:15:54.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:20:10.82	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
21:20:11.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:21:16.03	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
21:21:17.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:21:21.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:21:21.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:21:21.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:21:23.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:21:24.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:21:24.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:21:47.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -10c
21:34:46.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:34:46.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:34:46.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:34:48.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:34:49.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:34:49.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:34:52.07	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
21:34:53.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:36:37.33	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
21:36:38.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:40:03.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:40:03.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:40:03.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:40:05.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:40:06.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:40:06.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:45:47.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:45:47.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:45:47.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:45:50.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:45:50.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:45:51.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:45:56.80	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
21:45:58.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:47:29.35	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
21:47:30.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:47:37.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:47:37.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:47:37.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:47:39.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:47:40.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

21:47:40.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:53:18.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:53:18.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:53:18.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:53:19.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:53:20.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:53:21.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:53:22.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
21:53:44.35	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
21:53:45.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:54:01.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:55:15.90	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
21:55:16.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
22:03:38.71	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
22:03:39.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
22:04:54.70	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
22:05:27.34	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
22:05:31.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:05:31.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:05:31.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:05:33.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:05:33.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:05:33.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:09:15.24	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
22:09:16.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
22:10:16.91	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
22:10:22.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:10:22.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:10:22.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:10:23.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:10:24.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:10:25.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:14:58.65	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
22:14:59.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
22:16:19.87	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
22:16:20.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
22:16:29.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:16:29.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:16:29.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:16:30.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:16:31.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:16:32.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:22:16.03	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
22:22:17.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
22:23:30.28	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
22:23:31.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
22:23:56.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:23:56.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:23:56.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:23:57.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:23:57.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:23:58.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
22:23:59.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:24:00.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
22:24:06.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:24:08.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:25:27.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
22:25:49.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** start profile
22:44:14.79	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
22:44:19.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:44:19.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

22:44:19.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:44:20.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:44:22.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:44:22.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:44:26.58	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
22:44:26.60	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
22:44:30.68	USH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
22:44:30.69	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
22:44:34.34	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
22:44:34.36	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
22:44:36.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:44:36.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:44:36.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:44:39.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:44:41.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:44:41.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:44:57.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -11c
22:46:08.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -10c
22:46:11.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:46:11.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:46:11.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
22:46:14.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:46:15.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:46:16.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
22:59:04.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile start run
23:03:17.15	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
23:05:37.52	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
23:05:47.96	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
23:05:53.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:05:53.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:05:53.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:05:55.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:05:57.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:05:58.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:05:59.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:10:27.63	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
23:11:30.81	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
23:15:12.14	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
23:15:16.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:15:16.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:15:16.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:15:19.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:15:21.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:15:21.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:16:10.21	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
23:17:12.38	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
23:21:53.50	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
23:23:02.16	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
23:23:27.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:23:27.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:23:27.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:23:29.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:23:32.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:23:32.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:23:41.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -11c

23:27:19.06	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
23:28:33.47	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
23:29:50.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:29:50.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:29:50.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:29:52.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:29:54.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:29:54.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:33:30.28	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
23:35:02.05	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
23:35:07.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:35:07.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:35:07.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:35:10.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:35:12.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:35:12.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:39:30.22	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
23:40:31.16	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
23:40:37.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:40:38.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:40:38.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:40:40.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:40:42.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:40:43.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:45:45.42	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
23:46:52.43	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
23:47:03.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:47:03.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:47:03.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:47:06.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:47:08.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:47:08.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:51:35.53	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
23:52:50.64	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
23:53:47.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:53:47.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:53:47.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:53:50.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:53:51.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:53:52.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:57:28.94	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
23:58:35.61	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
23:59:13.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:59:13.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:59:13.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:59:16.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:59:17.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:59:18.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:03:33.67	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
00:04:39.16	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
00:05:02.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:05:03.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:05:03.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:05:03.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:05:06.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
00:05:07.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:05:07.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:06:18.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:09:17.73	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
00:10:41.56	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
00:10:46.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

00:10:46.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:10:46.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:10:47.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:10:48.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:10:51.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:10:52.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
00:12:04.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:16:24.15	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
00:18:25.04	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
00:18:33.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:18:34.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:18:34.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:18:34.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:18:37.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
00:18:38.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:18:38.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:18:40.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:21:15.35	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
00:22:16.82	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
00:22:21.57	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
00:22:28.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:22:28.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:22:28.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:22:30.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:22:32.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:22:33.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:22:37.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:22:38.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:22:38.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:22:40.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:22:42.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:22:43.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:26:59.43	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
00:28:12.04	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
00:28:24.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:28:24.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:28:24.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:28:26.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:28:28.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:28:29.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:32:59.86	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
00:34:30.59	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
00:34:59.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:34:59.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:34:59.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:35:01.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:35:03.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:35:04.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:38:55.92	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
00:40:03.31	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
00:44:54.79	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
00:45:59.53	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
00:50:55.93	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
00:52:00.85	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
00:53:04.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:53:04.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:53:04.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:53:06.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:53:09.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:53:09.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:58:32.75	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000

00:59:42.30	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
00:59:48.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:59:49.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:59:49.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
00:59:51.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:59:53.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
00:59:54.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:04:01.64	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
01:05:10.21	SWS	125.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
01:11:17.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:11:17.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:11:17.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:11:20.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:11:21.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:11:21.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:11:27.39	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
01:11:27.41	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
01:11:30.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:11:31.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:11:35.92	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
01:14:53.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
01:14:58.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:14:58.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:14:58.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:14:59.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:15:02.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:15:03.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:15:05.38	SWS	-	250	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
01:19:09.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run
01:20:21.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
01:20:33.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -11
01:20:37.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:20:37.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:20:37.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:20:39.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:20:42.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:20:42.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:24:20.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run
01:25:48.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
01:34:28.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** land Barrow 012854
01:34:30.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:34:30.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:34:30.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
01:34:32.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:34:35.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:34:35.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
01:34:39.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
01:34:39.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
01:34:40.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
01:34:45.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
01:34:47.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
01:34:48.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
01:34:58.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
01:35:01.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** SHUTTING DOWN...
01:35:01.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor control quit.
02:55:49.44	---	-	-	-	-	
02:55:49.44	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++

```

02:55:49.44 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn /
02:55:49.44 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B348
02:55:49.44 --- - - - -
02:56:03.22 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
02:56:03.31 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
02:56:03.40 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
02:56:20.52 SWS - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to
600ms.
02:56:22.92 SWS - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to
600ms.
02:56:25.82 USH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to
600ms.
02:56:27.73 USH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to
600ms.
02:56:30.87 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to
600ms.
02:56:33.00 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to
600ms.
02:56:52.77 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
02:56:52.78 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
02:56:52.78 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
02:57:03.40 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
02:57:10.59 SWS -0.0 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
02:57:12.25 SWS 173.3 - - - Telescope stopped.
02:57:22.65 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
02:57:22.91 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
02:57:23.18 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
02:57:23.47 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.
02:57:23.73 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.
02:57:24.01 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.
02:57:27.96 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
02:57:29.10 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
02:57:29.35 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
02:57:29.63 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
02:57:32.40 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
02:57:32.75 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
02:57:33.13 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
02:57:38.84 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
02:57:39.17 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
02:57:39.56 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
02:58:11.01 --- - - - - *** box temp -5c
03:00:29.64 SWS 125.3 - - - Telescope stopped.
03:01:27.74 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
03:01:29.87 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
03:01:32.28 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
03:01:34.39 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
03:01:36.29 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
03:01:39.98 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

03:01:40.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:01:40.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:01:46.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
03:01:46.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
03:01:46.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
03:01:49.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:01:49.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:01:50.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:08:26.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** t/o Barrow 030641
03:12:37.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -6
03:12:42.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:12:42.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:12:42.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:12:43.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
03:12:43.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
03:12:43.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
03:12:47.27	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
03:12:48.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:12:49.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:12:49.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:12:51.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:12:51.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:12:51.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:12:57.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:12:58.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:12:58.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:18:49.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:18:49.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:18:49.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:18:56.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:18:56.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:18:56.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:35:42.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile
03:36:20.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** end science
03:36:24.56	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
03:36:29.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:36:30.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:36:30.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
03:36:36.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:36:36.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:36:36.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
03:36:53.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -9c
03:37:13.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
03:37:13.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
03:37:13.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
03:37:18.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
03:37:20.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
03:37:21.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
03:37:25.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	ERROR: Could not disable telescope.
03:37:33.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** SHUTTING DOWN...
03:37:33.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor control quit.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B348 page 1 of
 Date: 23/02/08 Operator(s): JSS Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2
 Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments	
172444	Grnd		ASCII	Housekeeping			started	
182445	Grnd			clk				
182600	Grnd.	1/120	clk	7099	32.05		HBB cal	
182722	Grnd.	1/120	clk	7117	32.05		CBB cal.	
192003	Grnd.		HBB	Noise	check.		script.	
2003	Transa		HBB	Noise	check		script	
200648	Transa			cal	script	7064	20.46	
203600	Transa	1/120	CBB	clk.	7067	22.38		
203728	Transa	1/120	HBB	clk	7085	22.39		
204426	Transa			cal	script	7087	21.46	
204548	Transa	520/1	Zen	open				
5045	Transa		(w)	script				
			strange interferences - gentle stop on HBB data					
			will restart software					
7517			stopped housekeeping					
			No housekeeping data after software reboot					
			rebooted Interferometer					
			rebooted PC.					
210439			Restored all software ok finally					
211038			cal	script	clk	22.47	7065 hopefully CBB has settled enough	
211208	R1	520/1	Noe	clk	7074	22.39	FL280	
211638	R1			cal	script	clk	7066 21.42	
211814	R1	240/1	Noe	clk	7098			
212020	R1	120/1	Zen	open				
212140	R1	120/1	Noe	clk	7101	22.25		
212249	R1	1/120	HBB	clk			- funny shape to channel A	
212400	R1	1/120	CBB	clk	7074	22.35		
212443	R1	520/1	Noe	clk	7078	22.09		
212908	R1		(w)	script	7094	22.32		
213050	R1	400/1	Noe					
	R1		(w)	script				

ARIES flight log

Flight: 02/22/

page 2 of

Date: 23/2/09

Operator(s): Joss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CLXPT ASIA flight North of Barrow

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Fit ptrn	Scans	View	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Comments
213430	R1	CAWSCRIPT	PT		7077	22-36	
213534	R1	120/1	Zen	open	7064	21-40	
213645	R1	520/1	Nwd	Cbsd	7092	22-50	
214120	R1	CAWSCRIPT			7080	22-24	
214241	R1	360/1	Nwd				
214548	R1	120/1	Zen	open	7058	22-17	
214653	R1	CAWSCRIPT		Cbsd	7025	22-6	
214816	R1	520/1	Nwd	Cbsd	7061	21-71	
215245	R1	CAWSCRIPT					
215401	R1	120/1	Zen	open	7065	22-20	
215510	R1	360/1	Nwd	Cbsd	7087	22-75	
215815	R1	CAWSCRIPT		Cbsd	7097	22-47	
215932	R1	360/1	Nwd	Cbsd	7061	22-33	
220322	R1	120/1	Zen	open	7018	22-59	open @ 0355
220430	R1	CAWSCRIPT		Cbsd	7120	22-13	
220548	R1	400/1	Nwd	Cbsd	7098	22-15	
220912	R1	120/1	Zen				
221017	R1	CAWSCRIPT		Cbsd	7059	21-96	
221138	R1	400/1	Nwd	Cbsd	7079	23-01	
221507	R1	120/1	Zen	open	7071	22-83	
221610	R1	CAWSCRIPT		Cbsd	7075	21-98	
221732	R1	400/1	Nwd	Cbsd	7078	22-70	
222102	R1-1	CAWSCRIPT		Cbsd	7149	21-92	
222216	R1-1	120/1	Zen	open	7055	22-69	
222327	R1-1	400/1	Nwd	Cbsd	7090	22-58	
222529	R1-1	CAWSCRIPT		Cbsd	708	21-14	
222700	R2	CAWSCRIPT		Cbsd	7102	22-18	
222800	R2	400/1	Nwd	Cbsd	2208	71-31	100'
222809	R2	CAWSCRIPT		Cbsd	7094	21-77	
222916	R2	120/1	Zen	open	7103	22-17	
222925	R2	400/1	Nwd	Cbsd	7095	21-90	

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13348

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Date: 23/2/08

Operator(s): Joss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: AXII

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
230858	R2	Cal script			71-4	23-05	
23105	R2	120/1	zen	open	70-9	21-47	
231124	R2	400/1	Nwd	clsd	70-8	22-43	
231444	R2	Cal script			71-22	23-36	
231608	R2	120/1	zen	open	70-6	22-50	
231715	R2	400/1	Nwd	clsd	71-20	22-24	
232040	R2	Cal script			70-6	22-43	
232156	R2	120/1	zen	open	70-42	21-45	
222331	R2-1	300/1	Nwd	clsd	71-29	22-87	
222608	R2-1	Cal script dsd			70-86	21-88	
222730	R2-1	120/1	zen	open	70-94	22-08	
222816	R2-1	120/1	zen	open	70-96	22-21	
222925	R2-1	360/1	Nwd	clsd	71-1	22-55	
223227	R2-1	Cal script dsd			70-77	21-63	
223346	R2-1	120/1	zen	open	70-6	22-56	
223455	R2-1	400/1	Nwd	clsd	71-43	22-17	
223818		Cal script			70-91	21-4	
223935	R2-1	120/1	zen	open	71-03	22-00	
224059	R2-1	400/1	Nwd	clsd	71-1	22-46	
224425		Cal script			70-91	22-37	
224843	R2-1	120/1	zen	open	70-95	21-84	
224657	R2-1	400/1	Nwd	clsd			
225019		Cal script			70-74	21-31	
225139	R2-1	120/1	zen	open	70-80	22-14	
225250	R2-1	400/1	Nwd	clsd	70-84	22-34	
225613	R2-1	Cal script dsd			70-81	21-92	
225734	R2-1	120/1	zen	open	70-67	21-7	
225844	R2-1	400/1	Nwd	clsd	71-05	22-3	
220209	R2-1	Cal script dsd			70-86	21-82	
220326	R2-1	120/1	zen	open	70-89	22-11	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B348

page 4 of

Date: 23/2/08 Operator(s): Jess

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: ?

Loc./Notes: Alaska. CLP II

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Sht	HBB	CBB	Comments
000445	R2-1	400/1	Nae	clsd	70.56	22.66	
000804				Cal script			
000921	R2-1	120/1	Zen	open			
000943	R2-1	400/1	Nae	clsd	70.56	22.24	- switched ARIES off by mistake! Rebooted everything! Sorry.
001635	R2-1	400/1	Nae	clsd	77.4	30.9	Reminds to let cal rmp settle
001956	R2-1	Cal script	clsd		71.38	29.64	set CBB to 30°C
002115	R2-1	120/1	Zen	open	70.56	29.72	
002233	R2-1	400/1	Nae	clsd	70.79	30.87	
002557	R2-1	Cal script	clsd		71.13	30.50	
002712	R2-1	120/1	Zen	open	70.89	29.82	
002844	R2-1	400/1	Nae	clsd	70.86	30.26	
003148	R2-1	Cal script	clsd		70.70	30.23	
003305	R2-1	120/1	Zen	open	70.88	30.14	
003415	R2-1	400/1	Nae	clsd	70.61	30.34	
003743	R2-1	Cal script	clsd		70.77	30.59	
003859	R2-1	120/1	Zen	open	70.82	29.88	
004016	R2-1	400/1	Nae	clsd	71.24	30.10	
004338	R2-1	Cal script	clsd		71.06	30.86	
004457	R2-1	120/1	Zen	open	70.90	30.09	
004609	R2-1	400/1	Nae	clsd	70.96	30.21	
004943	R2-1	Cal script	clsd		71.06	31.02	
005055	R2-1	120/1	Zen	open	70.89	30.45	
005346	R2-1	400/1	Nae	clsd	70.99	30.43	
005709	R2-1	Cal script	clsd		71.04	30.62	
005819	R2-1	120/1	Zen	open	71.03	29.81	opened shutter lower
005928	R2-1	400/1	Nae	clsd	71.05	30.55	
010252	R2-1	Cal script	clsd		71.03	31.50	
010409	R2-1	120/1	Zen	open	70.70	30.41	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B348 page 5 of

Date: 23/2/08 Operator(s): JSS Res: K Gain A: 2B?

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
010524	R2-1	400/1	Need	(dsc)	708	30-23	
010851	R2-1	calscript	(dsc)		7-01	30-12	
011013	R2-1	520/1	Need	(dsc)	708	30-13	been into core
011450	R2-1	Gal script			7104	30-20	
	R3-1	400/1	Need	(dsc)			did not get start line.
012030	R3-1	400/1	calscript				
012420	R3-1	400/1	Need	(dsc)	724	30-74	
012548	R3-1	calscript			7060	92-84	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	23/02/08	Flight	B348	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	CLPX-II			
Departure	Fairbanks		Arrival	Fairbanks			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection							X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X
FERA on				at time	17:27		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	17.4°C	Ch	17.3°C	Ch18	16.8°C	
Temperature controller set points		50°C	17	50°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on				at time	17:34		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289.1	Cold	289.4			
Target heating							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	17:36		
Scan indication			Monitor	>	Visual		X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							X
Turn on Deimos CPU							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Start Deimos Software				at time	17:27		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289.3	Cold	289.8			
Target heating							X
Scan indication			Monitor	>	Visual		X
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$		at time		
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.57	Cold	290.06
	Deimos:	Hot	344.49	Cold	300.8
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	0	34.74	0	35.52	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)
	41.49	35.01	40.28	42.44	42.79

Power changeover

Headset on before start	
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)	
Exit Deimos Software (x)	
POWER CHANGEOVER	
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton
Restart Deimos Software	
System running again	at time

CVI log

2/23/08 5:31:34 PM B348 CLPX-II
2/23/08 8:18:43 PM The hygro was zeroed on the ground using the diluent air, but no
pressure pump. The signal level at fl240 is around -0.6 .
2/23/08 8:19:29 PM Hygro zeroed at FL240
2/23/08 8:31:08 PM Diluent level reduced to 0
2/23/08 8:32:22 PM Flow leves on PCASP inreased to account for altitude.
2/23/08 9:11:20 PM Start of run 1 at fl280
2/23/08 10:25:37 PM End of run 1
2/23/08 10:26:03 PM Decent to 1000 ft

Flight:

B348

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevezorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Report Created 12/03/2008
15:07:58

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Last Updated:

27/02/2008 02:17:51

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B348

Date: 23 February 2008

Instruments

1. Horace Display LAT/LONG not in agreement with either GIN, GPS or INU (which all agree).
2. Satcom problems during middle third of flight. May have been caused by degraded GPS?

Deimos: some problems, esp with 50GHz channel. Aries: minor issues only.

Aircraft

Extended Range checks caused logistical problems prior to take-off!
Number two flight GPS intermittent throughout latter half of the flight.

ISDN Emails

Nil connections

Satcom-H Calls

1 to report position and get met info as satcom had fallen over

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B348:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as any PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	01 Apr 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

3 x Rear/Downward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080223_b348_194121_25hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080223_b348_204302_25hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080223_b348_210206_25hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080223_b348_221632_25hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080223_b348_232006_25hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080224_b348_002203_25hz.avi

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080223_b348_194042_25hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080223_b348_204252_25hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080223_b348_210208_25hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080223_b348_221422_25hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080223_b348_221628_25hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080223_b348_231957_25hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080224_b348_002153_25hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080223_b348_194115_25hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080223_b348_204258_25hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080223_b348_210202_25hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080223_b348_221413_25hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080223_b348_221625_25hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080223_b348_232010_25hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080224_b348_002159_25hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080223_b348_194118_25hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080223_b348_204300_25hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080223_b348_210204_25hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080223_b348_221417_25hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080223_b348_221635_25hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080223_b348_232001_25hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080224_b348_002155_25hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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